

**MISTUNING IDENTIFICATION OF BLISKS USING MASS DETUNING
AND INFLUENCE COEFFICIENTS**

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ABSTRACT

Integrally bladed disks, also known as blisks, are important components in the operation of gas turbines. To study the dynamics of these structures, several computational techniques approximate blisks as tuned systems, where all blades have the same characteristics. In reality, manufactured blades have small variations from their intended design, thus creating so-called mistuned systems. Previous work has shown that such small variations can cause high response amplifications that can result in blisk structural failure. Therefore, it is essential to identify mistuning to ensure the safety operation of these systems. Several methods utilize cantilever blade frequencies in their procedure to model mistuning and calculate blisk vibration response. A previously developed mistuning identification method uses mass detuning to isolate the cantilever blade frequencies and a set of influence coefficients to quantify the blade-to-blade couplings. However, the mistuning is calculated with respect to an arbitrary mistuning value that later needs to be identified through a trial and error procedure that can affect the accuracy of the final mistuning values. This paper focuses on updating the method to eliminate this additive error that cannot precisely be determined. Furthermore, the updated procedure is applied to an as-manufactured blisk using experimental ping test results. An additional analysis is performed on the effect of adding multiple sets of influence coefficients to capture the blade-to-blade couplings more accurately.

Keywords: blisks, mistuning, system identification

1. INTRODUCTION

Integrally bladed disks, also known as blisks, are commonly used in turbomachinery [1] and are manufactured as a single component. Blisks are exposed to fluctuating aerodynamic forces in operation. Thus, understanding the structural dynamics

of blisks is essential to ensure the safe operation of these power systems [2]. To do so, several computational techniques have been developed to study the dynamics of these structures. Some of these techniques assume that the blades (and sectors) of a blisk have the same nominal characteristics, forming a so-called tuned system. Hence, tuned blisks are modeled as cyclic-symmetric structures [1,3] to predict their dynamics. However, manufactured blisks include unavoidable small variations from their nominal properties, thus forming a mistuned system [4,5]. Mistuning in blisks is often represented as variations in material properties of the blade (such as Young's modulus) [6]. These small variations can cause significant vibration response amplification that can result in high-cycle fatigue failure of the blisk [1]. To study response amplification due to mistuning and model mistuned blisk dynamics, finite-element (FE) models are often used and can contain millions of degrees-of-freedom (DoFs), which are computationally cumbersome. To address this challenge, reduced-order models (ROMs) have been developed for simulating mistuned blisk dynamics [7–15].

To use these ROMs to predict the dynamics of an as-manufactured mistuned blisk requires the identification (ID) of mistuning. As such, several mistuning identification methods have been developed [2,4,9,16,17]. Blade-by-blade techniques involve applying masses to detune all blades except for one that we seek to isolate and measure [2,18]. For each isolated blade, a cantilever-blade mode shape is used to approximate the blade-alone frequency. An impact excitation (i.e., ping test) is applied to the isolated blade of the blisk and the response is measured to compute the frequency response function (FRF). This process is then repeated for each blade individually. However, because blisks are a single piece, it can be difficult to obtain a mode that perfectly isolates a blade and does not present any motion in the other blades (with attached masses). Thus, several methods have been developed to account for coupling among blades [9,18–20]

One method [18] models the blisk using two DoFs in each sector. The coupling stiffness and the blade stiffness are obtained by computing an FRF of this discrete model and comparing it with the experimental FRF. Another procedure [19] utilizes a tuned FE model of the blisk. An iterative process is implemented by changing the Young's modulus of each blade to match the FRFs obtained experimentally with those obtained from the FE model with isolation masses attached. Another recent approach [2] determines a set of influence coefficients that quantify the coupling between the isolated blade and the other blades. Using the influence coefficients and resonance frequencies from measured FRFs of the blisk with masses added, a system of equations is formulated to identify mistuning. However, the mistuning values obtained use as reference an arbitrary value for one of the blades, creating an unidentified (additive) value that cannot be easily determined. This value is a cyclic modeling error. This paper extends the method proposed in [2] and applies the updated method to an as-manufactured blisk and discusses additional improvements.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Mistuning definition

As presented in [2], mistuning is commonly represented as a variation in the cantilever-blade frequencies of the blisk from its nominal values. This can be expressed mathematically as:

$$\delta_i^\omega = \frac{\omega_i - \omega_{nominal}}{\omega_{nominal}}. \quad (1)$$

For small mistuning values, δ_i^ω can also be approximated as the difference in the eigenvalues corresponding to a mistuned and nominal cantilever blade mode of the blade alone, namely

$$\delta_i = \frac{\omega_i^2 - \omega_{nominal}^2}{\omega_{nominal}^2}. \quad (2)$$

This expression, as observed in [2], is actually defining a small perturbation in the stiffness matrix of a blisk's blade corresponding to cantilever-blade mode i . Typically, this perturbation is represented as a change in the Young's modulus of the blade, and is the approach used throughout this paper. Thus, for small variations between the mistuned and nominal cantilever beam frequencies of a blade, mistuning can be expressed as

$$\frac{E_i - E_{nominal}}{E_{nominal}} = \delta_i = \frac{\omega_i^2 - \omega_{nominal}^2}{\omega_{nominal}^2}, \quad (3)$$

where E_i is the Young's modulus of mistuned blade i (corresponding to cantilever blade mode i), and $E_{nominal}$ is the Young's modulus of the nominal blade.

2.2 Background of coefficient identification method

To identify mistuning, it is first important to characterize the eigenvalues of the isolated blade modes (cantilever blade

modes). To do so, a common procedure is to attach masses on all the blades except for the one to be isolated. Ideally, the motion of other blades is prevented entirely, and effectively allows the isolated blade to be measured independently. However, previous studies have shown that in practice complete isolation of one blade can be very difficult to achieve, therefore preventing the ability to induce a pure cantilever blade mode of one single blade [18,19]. Lupini et. al [2] determined a formula through which the coupling between the isolated blade and those with masses attached is quantified and included in the mistuning identification, given as

$$\frac{\omega_i^2 - \omega_{ref}^2}{\omega_{ref}^2} = am + \sum_{k=\alpha}^{\beta} b_k \delta_{i+k}, \quad (4)$$

where ω_i is the blade i cantilever-beam mode frequency when blade i is isolated, ω_{ref} is a reference blisk frequency value, δ_{i+k} is the mistuning of the blade located k blades away from isolated blade i and b_k is its respective influence coefficient. This coefficient is introduced to quantify the contribution of this blade to the cantilever-beam mode frequency corresponding to isolated blade i . α is a negative integer whose absolute value corresponds to the number of blades situated clockwise from blade i and whose contributions to the cantilever-beam mode frequency of blade i are included. Similarly, β is a positive integer that corresponds to the number of blades situated counterclockwise from blade i and whose contributions are included. m is the mass of the isolation masses used and a is a real number quantifying the contribution of the mass added.

The identification of the influence coefficients will be discussed in section 2.4. For now, we will consider that their values have already been identified. Following the approach presented in [2], Eq. (4) is applied separately for a general blade with index t and a general blade with index r , and the latter's expression subtracted from the former's, resulting in:

$$\frac{\omega_t^2 - \omega_r^2}{\omega_{ref}^2} = \sum_{k=\alpha}^{\beta} b_k (\delta_{t+k} - \delta_{r+k}). \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) is applied for $r = 1$ and for $t = 2, 3, \dots, N$, where N is the total number of blades. δ_r (i.e. the mistuning of blade r) is set to 0 to reduce the system from $N - 1$ equations and N unknowns to $N - 1$ equations and $N - 1$ unknowns. Furthermore, ω_{ref} is chosen as ω_1 . Equation (5) becomes

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_0 - b_1 & b_1 - b_2 & \dots & b_{-2} - b_{-1} \\ b_{-1} - b_1 & b_0 - b_2 & & b_{-3} - b_{-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ b_2 - b_1 & b_3 - b_2 & \dots & b_0 - b_{-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta_2 \\ \delta_3 \\ \vdots \\ \delta_N \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\omega_2^2 - \omega_1^2}{\omega_1^2} \\ \frac{\omega_3^2 - \omega_1^2}{\omega_1^2} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\omega_N^2 - \omega_1^2}{\omega_1^2} \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) is solved for the $N - 1$ mistuning values (all blades except for δ_1). Thus, a so-called cyclic modeling error, defined as a shift in all mistuning values, is created because we assume a reference mistuning value (here, a nominal Young's

modulus) which may not match that of the underlying FE model and/or as-manufactured blisk. To quantify and identify this error, one possibility, similar to [19], is measure the FRF of the blisk under investigation with isolation masses added (on all blades, but one). The next step is to apply the identified mistuning to the tuned computational model of the blisk being investigated and compute its FRF when the same blade is isolated. All originally identified mistuning values should be incremented by different ε values (ε is a real number) and applied to the mistuned computational model until the FRF of this blisk computational model with the previously selected isolated blade matches the response of the investigated blisk with the same blade isolated. The final value obtained for ε will be the shift (i.e., the cyclic modeling error) that needs to be added to all the initially identified mistuning values δ_t for $t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$.

2.3 Enhanced coefficient identification method

Starting from the original methodology in the previous section, the goal of the enhanced method proposed here is to avoid the creation of the cyclic modeling error and to directly identify the mistuning values corresponding to all blades. This enhanced method, like that originally presented in [2], accounts for the fact that the perturbed eigenvalue of a blisk having one isolated blade is a function of the amount of isolation mass used and the blisk mistuning values. To show this, consider a Taylor series expansion in variables m and δ of the eigenvalue of the blisk λ with one blade isolated, expressed as

$$\lambda(m, \delta) = \lambda(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta_{\text{ref}}) + (m - m_{\text{ref}}) \frac{\partial \lambda(m, \delta)}{\partial m} \Big|_{(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta_{\text{ref}})} + \sum_{k=\alpha}^{\beta} (\delta_{i+k} - \delta_{i+k, \text{ref}}) \frac{\partial \lambda(m, \delta)}{\partial \delta_{i+k}} \Big|_{(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta_{\text{ref}})} + \text{H. O. T.}, \quad (7)$$

where $\lambda = \omega_i^2(m, \delta)$ is the eigenvalue of the blisk mistuned in all its N blades with $\delta = [\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_N]$ and with blade i isolated using mass m applied to $N - 1$ blades, δ_{ref} is the mistuning cyclic modeling error, $\delta_{\text{ref}} = [\delta_1^{\text{ref}}, \delta_2^{\text{ref}}, \dots, \delta_N^{\text{ref}}]$, where $\delta_1^{\text{ref}} = \delta_2^{\text{ref}} = \dots = \delta_N^{\text{ref}} = \delta_1^{\text{ref}}$. The partial derivatives are

$$\frac{\partial \lambda(m, \delta)}{\partial m} \Big|_{(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta_{\text{ref}})} = a \lambda(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta_{\text{ref}}), \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial \lambda(m, \delta)}{\partial \delta_{i+k}} \Big|_{(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta_{\text{ref}})} = b_k \lambda(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta_{\text{ref}}). \quad (9)$$

Substituting Eqs. (8) and (9) into Eq. (7) and assuming negligible contributions from higher-order terms (H.O.T.) in Eq. (7) such that they can be ignored, one obtains

$$\lambda(m, \delta) = \lambda(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta_{\text{ref}}) + a(m - m_{\text{ref}}) \lambda(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta_{\text{ref}}) + \lambda(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta_{\text{ref}}) \sum_{k=\alpha}^{\beta} b_k (\delta_{i+k} - \delta_{i+k, \text{ref}}), \quad (10)$$

where a and b_k are real scalar influence coefficients.

Next, choose as reference a tuned blisk with isolation mass m_{ref} added, and choose $m = m_{\text{ref}}$. Thus, Eq. (10) becomes

$$\frac{\omega_i^2(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta) - \omega_i^2(m_{\text{ref}}, \mathbf{0})}{\omega_i^2(m_{\text{ref}}, \mathbf{0})} = \sum_{k=\alpha}^{\beta} b_k \delta_{i+k} \quad (11)$$

It is important to notice that the formulation presented in Eq. (11) has eliminated the isolation mass term in Eq. (4) and uses as reference the eigenvalue corresponding to a tuned blisk with isolation masses added on all blades except for blade i , and denoted by $\omega_i^2(m_{\text{ref}}, \mathbf{0})$. In the following steps, we show that these modifications allow for direct identification of the blisk mistuning. Since the reference eigenvalue corresponds to a blisk with masses added, $\omega_i(m_{\text{ref}}, \mathbf{0})$ can be defined as simply ω_{ref} for all blade indices i .

2.4 Influence coefficients

To identify the influence coefficients b_k , a procedure similar to that presented in [2] is implemented using the newly formulated Eq. (11).

Firstly, a mass value to be used for isolation throughout the analysis is selected. As noted in [2], there is no general rule for how to select an isolation mass. However, considering the limited blade surface available for most blisks, a lighter, smaller mass is desirable in experiments. Furthermore, as discussed in [2], it was observed that a highly isolated cantilever beam mode does not necessarily provide a higher accuracy in the final mistuning identification. Thus, the goal is to choose a light mass that can generate a mode with a larger displacement in the isolated blade than in those with masses added. The amount of mass used for the studies in this work is discussed in Section 2.6.

Secondly, after selecting the isolation mass and the mode to be used for identification, n mistuning patterns are applied sequentially to the computational FE model of the blisk under investigation. A mistuning pattern is defined as

$$\mathbf{p}_n = [\delta_{i+\alpha}^n \ \delta_{i+\alpha+1}^n \ \dots \ \delta_{i-1}^n \ \delta_i^n \ \delta_{i+1}^n \ \dots \ \delta_{i+\beta-1}^n \ \delta_{i+\beta}^n]. \quad (12)$$

Note that the isolation blade is kept the same for each mistuning pattern applied to the computational blisk model. Thus, a modal analysis of the computational model of the blisk with isolation masses added is performed for each mistuning pattern applied. The eigenvalue corresponding to the previously selected mode is retained as $\omega_i^2(m_{\text{ref}}, \mathbf{p}_n)$, where m_{ref} is the isolation mass selected to be used throughout the analysis.

Finally, Eq. (11) is applied for each of the n mistuning patterns, using the eigenvalues obtained from the modal analysis.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{c} \frac{\omega_i^2(m_{\text{ref}}, \mathbf{p}_1) - \omega_{\text{ref}}^2}{\omega_{\text{ref}}^2} \\ \frac{\omega_i^2(m_{\text{ref}}, \mathbf{p}_2) - \omega_{\text{ref}}^2}{\omega_{\text{ref}}^2} \\ \frac{\omega_i^2(m_{\text{ref}}, \mathbf{p}_3) - \omega_{\text{ref}}^2}{\omega_{\text{ref}}^2} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\omega_i^2(m_{\text{ref}}, \mathbf{p}_n) - \omega_{\text{ref}}^2}{\omega_{\text{ref}}^2} \end{array} \right\} = \left[\begin{array}{cccc} \delta_{i+\alpha}^1 & \delta_{i+\alpha+1}^1 & \dots & \delta_{i+\beta}^1 \\ \delta_{i+\alpha}^2 & \delta_{i+\alpha+1}^2 & \dots & \delta_{i+\beta}^2 \\ \delta_{i+\alpha}^3 & \delta_{i+\alpha+1}^3 & \dots & \delta_{i+\beta}^3 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \delta_{i+\alpha}^n & \delta_{i+\alpha+1}^n & \dots & \delta_{i+\beta}^n \end{array} \right] \left\{ \begin{array}{c} b_\alpha \\ b_{\alpha+1} \\ \vdots \\ b_\beta \end{array} \right\}. \quad (13)$$

Equation (13) is solved for all influence coefficients, where the system of equations for n mistuning patterns is $\alpha + \beta + 1$. Additionally, note that $n = \alpha + \beta + 1$ is only the minimum number of mistuning patterns needed to ensure a unique solution for Eq. (13) (assuming the matrix of mistuning values is full rank). One can also include more mistuning patterns (i.e., $n > \alpha + \beta + 1$), resulting in an overdetermined system of equations. In that case, Eq. (13) can be solved in a least-squares sense by minimizing the sum of the square of the residuals.

2.5 Mistuning identification

To identify an unknown blisk mistuning pattern, Eq. 11 is applied N times, each iteration corresponding to one isolated blade. Using the previously identified coefficients from solving Eq. 13, the system to be solved becomes:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\omega_1^2(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta) - \omega_{\text{ref}}^2}{\omega_{\text{ref}}^2} \\ \frac{\omega_2^2(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta) - \omega_{\text{ref}}^2}{\omega_{\text{ref}}^2} \\ \frac{\omega_3^2(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta) - \omega_{\text{ref}}^2}{\omega_{\text{ref}}^2} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\omega_N^2(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta) - \omega_{\text{ref}}^2}{\omega_{\text{ref}}^2} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b_0 & b_1 & \dots & b_{-1} \\ b_{-1} & b_0 & & b_{-2} \\ b_{-2} & b_{-1} & \ddots & b_{-3} \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ b_1 & b_2 & \dots & b_0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta_1 \\ \delta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \delta_N \end{Bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

with $\delta = [\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_N]$, the vector of mistuning values to be identified. After solving the system in Eq. (14), the final mistuning values are identified, without creating any cyclic modeling error.

2.6 Computational and experimental applications

Two blisks are utilized for validating this updated mistuning identification method. The first is a blisk with 24 blades which will be referred to as the UofM blisk, presented in Fig. 1. The second is a blisk with 22 blades, referred to as the OSU Rotor 67 blisk [21] Fig. 1.

First, this method is applied for the computational FE model of the UofM blisk. To do so, a predefined surrogate mistuning vector δ is applied to the blisk by changing the Young's modulus of each blade (i.e., $\frac{E_i - E_{\text{nominal}}}{E_{\text{nominal}}} = \delta_i$ as expressed in Eq. (3)). The validation consists of applying this updated method to identify the predefined surrogate mistuning. To determine the influence coefficients, n mistuning patterns are applied iteratively to the tuned UofM blisk computational model and a modal analysis is performed for each of the n mistuned blisks. To ensure that the system in Eq. (13) is a fully determined system of equations, the number of mistuning patterns n is chosen to be equal to the number of coefficients used, N . For simplicity and computational efficiency when performing the modal analyses, the mistuning patterns chosen to determine the influence coefficients are of the form $\mathbf{p}_k = [\delta_1^k \delta_2^k \dots \delta_N^k]$, where $\delta_i^k = 0$ if $i \neq k$ and $\delta_i^k = 1\%$ if $i = k$, where $i, k \in$

FIGURE 1. UofM blisk (left) and OSU Rotor 67 blisk (right)

$\{1, 2, 3, \dots, N\}$. The isolation mass used in this analysis was $m_{\text{ref}} = 8$ grams (8g) distributed at the corners of the blade leading edge and trailing edge, where most kinetic energy is stored.

Second, the method is applied to the computational model of the OSU blisk at trailing edge corner, using the same procedure as that used for the UofM blisk. $m_{\text{ref}} = 4\text{g}$ was used throughout the application of and for all analyses using the OSU blisk.

Third, this method is applied to the as-manufactured OSU blisk. The influence coefficients identified from the OSU blisk computational model analyses are used in the experimental identification. The next step in the experimental analysis is to identify the $\omega_i(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta)$ frequency (from Eq. (14)) for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$ where $\omega_i(m_{\text{ref}}, \delta)$ is the frequency of the cantilever-blade mode corresponding to isolated blade i , using $m_{\text{ref}} = 4\text{g}$. To determine these frequencies, experimental ping testing was performed.

Sequentially, each blade is isolated using 4g magnets applied at the trailing edge corners of the other 21 titanium blades. A modal hammer is used to excite each isolated blade at its tip. The responses are measured using a calibrated capacitance probe. The trailing edge of each airfoil was struck with the calibrated hammer and the response of the struck airfoil was measured. The input force and output displacement were measured and bandpass filtering between 0.5 Hz and 30 kHz was applied. A gain was applied to maximize the resolution of the instrumentation response prior to feeding the response to the analog to digital converter.

The OSU Rotor 67 blisk was secured to a stand of similar stiffness and diameter as a shaft that will be used in rotating experiments. The stand was then securely bolted to the large test table and the experiment was electrically grounded to minimize noise in the capacitance probe.

The airfoils were struck with a steel tipped hammer and the free response was then measured for a minimum of five seconds. Multiple samples were collected to ensure repeatability and allow for better noise reduction in post-processing. Other locations besides the tip trailing edge were also investigated for testing. These other locations included the leading edge, mid-chord, mid span, and airfoil root. The tip trailing edge was selected for final testing for its ease of access and responsiveness to several mode families.

A frequency response function was calculated for each airfoil, with the application of isolation magnets. The frequency response function was used to calculate natural frequencies of several mode families and to qualitatively check for errors such as random noise. A single degree of freedom fit is performed for

FIGURE 2. OSU blisk experimental setup

each peak corresponding to the mode used in the identification analysis. Thus, the cantilever blade like frequencies were determined.

After experimentally identifying the eigenvalues corresponding to the mode used for the influence coefficient identification, they are input in Eq. (14) as $\omega_i^2(m_{ref}, \delta)$ for each $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$. Finally, the blisk mistuning vector $\delta = [\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_N]$ is identified by solving Eq. (14).

From this point, a blisk having isolation masses added, signifies that the blisk has the same amount of mass attached at all its blades, but one, the isolated blade, that is free.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 UofM blisk computational results

The first blisk to be analyzed is the UofM blisk. As mentioned in section 2.4, the first step is to identify the mass value for blade isolation and the corresponding mode to be used throughout the analysis. The mode selected in the analysis can be visualized in Fig. 3. Whilst other modes presented better isolation when masses were added, the peculiarity of this mode comes from the significant motion present in the rest of the blades. Thus, this mode is a perfect candidate for applying the updated mistuning ID method when strong couplings are present. The influence coefficients are calculated using Eq. 13 and are presented in Fig. 4. To check the validity of the influence coefficients, it can be observed that the highest motion in the mode at 2350Hz is captured at the blades furthest away from the isolated one. This is substantiated by Fig 4. which shows the largest coefficients b_k at $k = -12$ and $k = 11$. A surrogate mistuning pattern \mathbf{p}_{UofM} is applied to the UofM blisk. Mistuning identification is performed by applying Eq. (14) using $\delta = \mathbf{p}_{UofM}$ and the influence coefficients previously identified.

FIGURE 3. UofM blisk mode selected at 2350 Hz

FIGURE 4. UofM blisk – influence coefficients b_k

In Fig. 5 the identified mistuning is presented together with \mathbf{p}_{UofM} , the mistuning pattern to be identified. The error in the identification was computed using Eq. (15), where \mathbf{p}_{UofM, ID_i} is the mistuning value identified at blade i and \mathbf{p}_{UofM_i} is the surrogate mistuning value at blade i .

FIGURE 5. UofM mistuning identification

It can be observed that overall, the identification is very close to the applied surrogate mistuning, with errors below 15% for most of the blades. It is important to mention that the identified mistuning does not include any cyclic modelling error

that would need to be determined through trial and error in order to complete the identification process.

$$\text{Error} = \frac{|p_{UofM, ID_i} - p_{UofM_i}|}{\max(p_{UofM})} \times 100\% \quad (15)$$

FIGURE 6. Error UofM mistuning identification

3.2 OSU blisk computational results

The next blisk to be analyzed is the OSU Rotor 67 blisk, presented in Fig. 1. The mode used for this analysis is presented in Fig. 7. It can be noticed that there is less motion in the rest of the blades of the structure, suggesting that there is less coupling present than in the mode selected for the UofM blisk.

Since the identification will also be performed on the as

FIGURE 7. OSU blisk mode selected at 410 Hz

manufactured model of the OSU blisk, it is important to test that the selected mode is isolated enough from other responding modes when performing experimental ping tests. To verify this, a frequency response function (FRF) of the tuned (i.e. $\delta_i = 0, \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$) computational model with isolation masses added was performed to verify if the selected mode responds when the isolated blade is excited at mid chord, blade tip. Results in Fig. 8 show that the 410 Hz mode selected is one of the two modes that respond in a broad frequency range. Furthermore, it is confirmed that the closest mode has a frequency of

approximately 388 Hz (Mode^{tuned,1}), far enough from the mode selected at 410 Hz (Mode^{tuned,2}).

FIGURE 8. FRF of tuned OSU blisk with isolation masses added

The next step in the identification process involves determining the influence coefficients as described in section 2.4. The coefficients can be visualized in Fig. 9. As previously checked for the UofM blisk, it can be observed that the blades further away from the isolated blade ($k = -10$ and $k = 10$) have the highest influence coefficients, can be observed by the larger blade responses occurring on the opposite side of the isolated blade in the mode shape shown in from Fig. 7.

FIGURE 9. OSU blisk – influence coefficients b_k

FIGURE 10. OSU blisk mistuning identification

A surrogate mistuning pattern \mathbf{p}_{OSU} is applied to the computational model of the OSU blisk and Eq. (14) is then applied to validate the updated mistuning identification method. The mistuning identified is once again very close to the prescribed surrogate mistuning, with errors below 10% for most of the blade mistuning. Furthermore, it is necessary to mention that these errors are calculated as percentages of percentage deviations from nominal Young’s modulus. For example, an error of 14% for δ_7 (the largest one in the OSU blisk analysis) calculated using Eq. (15) corresponds to approximately 0.03% difference between the nominal and the identified mistuning values, creating a difference of 1 Hz or less from the tuned

FIGURE 11. Error in OSU mistuning identification

frequency for this blisk.

3.3 OSU blisk experimental results

The updated mistuning identification method is also applied to the as manufactured OSU Rotor 67 blisk. The influence coefficients determined in the computational model are also used in the experimental method, as discussed in section 2.6. Furthermore, the identification is performed using Eq. 14, similarly to how it was applied for the computational models. The values of $\omega_i^2(m_{ref}, \delta)$ are captured experimentally, after performing ping tests on each isolated blade. Ten ping tests are performed for each isolated blade, computing the FRF and capturing the frequency corresponding to the mode shown in Fig. 6 for each trial. Finally, $\omega_i^2(m_{ref}, \delta)$ is retained as the average of the ten trials when blade i is isolated. Eq. (14) is applied using the experimental isolated blade frequencies $\omega_i^2(m_{ref}, \delta)$ and the influence coefficients determined in section 3.2, resulting in the identified mistuning $\delta_{OSU,exp}^{ID}$ presented in Fig. 12.

Since the identification is performed for the as manufactured blisk, it is not possible to compare the identified mistuning with the nominal mistuning of the blisk’s blades. However, the accuracy of the identified mistuning is evaluated using the computational OSU blisk model. To be more precise, the identified mistuning $\delta_{OSU,exp}^{ID}$ is first applied to the computational blisk. In addition, each blade of the computational mistuned blisk is sequentially isolated using the 4g mass utilized in the identification process and the computational blisk FRF is calculated for each isolation when the isolated blade is excited at

FIGURE 12. As manufactured OSU blisk mistuning identification mid chord, blade tip. There are two cantilever blade like mistuned blisk modes responding when blade i is isolated whose frequencies are retained as $\omega_i^{ID,1}$ and $\omega_i^{ID,2}$, $\omega_i^{ID,1} < \omega_i^{ID,2}$, $i \in \{1,2,3, \dots, 22\}$.

In Fig. 13, the FRFs corresponding to the ten ping tests of the as manufactured OSU blisk with blade 1 isolated are plotted. As mentioned in the previous section, the isolated blade is excited at its tip at mid chord. It is observed that while the second mode in the experimental FRF responds at almost the same frequency as $\omega_1^{ID,2}$, the first mode responds at a frequency lower than $\omega_1^{ID,1}$. The same pattern is noticed in Fig. 14 where the experimental FRFs of the as manufactured blisk with blade 22

FIGURE 13. Experimental FRFs OSU blisk with blade 1 isolated

FIGURE 14. Experimental FRFs OSU blisk with blade 22 isolated

isolated are plotted. While the second mode responds at the same frequency as $\omega_{22}^{ID,2}$, the first one is shifted to the left by approximately 10 Hz.

The frequency shift between the first mode responding in the experimental FRF of the as manufactured blisk and in the computational FRF of the OSU blisk mistuned with $\delta_{OSU,exp}^{ID}$ is presented for each isolation blade case in Fig. 15. The shift in frequency for the second mode responding is plotted in Fig. 16.

FIGURE 15. Frequency shift in mode 1

FIGURE 16. Frequency shift in mode 2

In both Fig. 15 and Fig. 16 the shifts are normalized by the maximum frequency captured from the experimental FRF for mode 1 and mode 2 respectively.

The frequency shift for the second mode responding is very small, hence this particular mode is captured properly when the blisk is mistuned with $\delta_{OSU,exp}^{ID}$. However, the first mode experiences a high frequency shift suggesting that the identified mistuning is not equal to the mistuning present in the experimental blisk. In addition, an important observation is that throughout the analysis the identification was performed using the second responding mode. Since this mode responds at the same frequency for both the experimental and the computational mistuned blisk with each blade sequentially isolated, it can be inferred that the identification properly identified the mistuning that would satisfy the response frequencies of this mode. Under the assumption that there are no other types of mistuning (e.g. geometric mistuning) or that the computational model accurately depicts the experimental OSU blisk (i.e., boundary conditions,

physical dimensions, structural properties), the first shift in the first mode should be close to 0. Hence, it is concluded that the computational model needs to be updated to match the experimental blisk model. It is paramount to emphasize that since the mode utilized throughout the identification process was almost perfectly identified when applying the mistuning $\delta_{OSU,exp}^{ID}$ to the blisk with isolation masses added, the identification was successful under the assumption that the computational OSU blisk accurately models the as manufactured one.

3.4 Improvements to the mistuning ID method

The updated mistuning identification method has its foundation from the Taylor series expansion of the eigenvalue of a blisk mode (chosen as mentioned in section 2.4) with one isolated blade. This eigenvalue $\lambda(m, \delta)$ is considered to be a function of the blisk mistuning and the isolation mass quantity. In section 2.3, the expansion is limited to only using the linear terms of the Taylor series. In this section, the focus is to analyze the effect of adding second order terms on the accuracy of the identification as presented in Eq. (16), namely

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda(m, \delta) = & \lambda(m_{ref}, \delta_{ref}) + (m - m_{ref}) \frac{\partial \lambda(m, \delta)}{\partial m} \Big|_{(m_{ref}, \delta_{ref})} + \\ & \sum_{k=\alpha}^{\beta} (\delta_{i+k} - \delta_{i+k,ref}) \frac{\partial \lambda(m, \delta)}{\partial \delta_{i+k}} \Big|_{(m_{ref}, \delta_{ref})} + \\ & (m - m_{ref})^2 \frac{\partial^2 \lambda(m, \delta)}{\partial^2 m} \Big|_{(m_{ref}, \delta_{ref})} + \\ & (m - m_{ref}) \sum_{k=\alpha}^{\beta} (\delta_{i+k} - \delta_{i+k,ref}) \frac{\partial^2 \lambda(m, \delta)}{\partial m \partial \delta_{i+k}} \Big|_{(m_{ref}, \delta_{ref})} + \\ & \sum_{r=\alpha}^{\beta} (\delta_{i+r} - \delta_{i+r,ref}) \sum_{k=\alpha}^{\beta} (\delta_{i+k} - \delta_{i+k,ref}) \\ & \frac{\partial^2 \lambda(m, \delta)}{\partial \delta_{i+r} \partial \delta_{i+k}} \Big|_{(m_{ref}, \delta_{ref})} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \lambda(m, \delta)}{\partial \delta_{i+r} \partial \delta_{i+k}} \Big|_{(m_{ref}, \delta_{ref})} = c_{kr} \lambda(m_{ref}, \delta_{ref}) \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{\partial \lambda(m, \delta)}{\partial \delta_{i+k}} \Big|_{(m_{ref}, \delta_{ref})} = b_k \lambda(m_{ref}, \delta_{ref}) \quad (18)$$

Similar to the procedure in Section 2.3, after choosing a tuned blisk (i.e. $\delta_{ref} = \mathbf{0}$) with isolation mass m_{ref} added, we substitute Eq. (17) and Eq. (18) into Eq. (16) and we get:

$$\frac{\omega_i^2(m_{ref}, \delta) - \omega^2(m_{ref}, \mathbf{0})}{\omega^2(m_{ref}, \mathbf{0})} = \sum_{k=\alpha}^{\beta} b_k \delta_{i+k} + \sum_{k=\alpha}^{\beta} \sum_{r=\alpha}^{\beta} c_{kr} \delta_{i+k} \delta_{i+r} \quad (19)$$

where $\omega_i(m, \delta)$ is the frequency of the blisk mode chosen with blade i isolated.

To identify the influence coefficients b_k and c_{kr} , a linear system is solved in Eq. (20), using mistuning patterns \mathbf{p}_j , $j \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, R\}$, where R should be equal to the number of influence coefficients to ensure a unique solution if matrix \mathbf{A} is full rank.

However, to identify all coefficients, a large number of mistuning patterns is necessary (e.g. for a blisk with 24 blades, 324 influence coefficients are present if second order terms are included). To avoid using such a large number of mistuning patterns, one could add only a small subset of second order terms and analyze if there is any improvement in accuracy compared to when using only linear terms.

After identifying the influence coefficients, they are introduced in Eq. (19). This equation is applied for each case when each blade is isolated, forming a nonlinear system of $N =$ number of blades equations that needs to be solved to identify the blisk mistuning δ . Future work involves identifying the optimal number of influence coefficients corresponding to the second order terms in Eq. (19) that would improve the accuracy of the mistuning identification.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{\omega_i^2(m_{ref,p1}) - \omega_{ref}^2}{\omega_{ref}^2} \\ \frac{\omega_i^2(m_{ref,p2}) - \omega_{ref}^2}{\omega_{ref}^2} \\ \frac{\omega_i^2(m_{ref,p3}) - \omega_{ref}^2}{\omega_{ref}^2} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\omega_i^2(m_{ref,pR}) - \omega_{ref}^2}{\omega_{ref}^2} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{A} \begin{pmatrix} b_\alpha \\ b_{\alpha+1} \\ \vdots \\ c_{\alpha\alpha} \\ c_{\alpha\alpha+1} \\ \vdots \\ c_{\alpha\beta} \\ c_{\alpha+1\alpha+1} \\ \vdots \\ c_{\alpha+1\beta} \\ \vdots \\ c_{\beta\beta} \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{i+\alpha}^1 & \dots & \delta_{i+\beta}^1 & \delta_{i+\alpha}^1 \delta_{i+\alpha}^1 & \dots & \delta_{i+\alpha}^1 \delta_{i+\alpha+\beta}^1 & \delta_{i+\alpha+1}^1 \delta_{i+\alpha+1}^1 & \dots & \delta_{i+\beta}^1 \delta_{i+\beta}^1 \\ \delta_{i+\alpha}^2 & \dots & \delta_{i+\beta}^2 & \delta_{i+\alpha}^2 \delta_{i+\alpha}^2 & \dots & \delta_{i+\alpha}^2 \delta_{i+\alpha+\beta}^2 & \delta_{i+\alpha+1}^2 \delta_{i+\alpha+1}^2 & \dots & \delta_{i+\beta}^2 \delta_{i+\beta}^2 \\ \delta_{i+\alpha}^3 & \dots & \delta_{i+\beta}^3 & \delta_{i+\alpha}^3 \delta_{i+\alpha}^3 & \dots & \delta_{i+\alpha}^3 \delta_{i+\alpha+\beta}^3 & \delta_{i+\alpha+1}^3 \delta_{i+\alpha+1}^3 & \dots & \delta_{i+\beta}^3 \delta_{i+\beta}^3 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \delta_{i+\alpha}^R & \dots & \delta_{i+\beta}^R & \delta_{i+\alpha}^R \delta_{i+\alpha}^R & \dots & \delta_{i+\alpha}^R \delta_{i+\alpha+\beta}^R & \delta_{i+\alpha+1}^R \delta_{i+\alpha+1}^R & \dots & \delta_{i+\beta}^R \delta_{i+\beta}^R \end{bmatrix}$$

4. CONCLUSIONS

An enhanced mistuning identification method using influence coefficients was developed expanding on previous work [2]. The main idea of the enhanced method is to express the mistuning of each blisk blade using the cantilever beam like mode of the blades. To obtain these specific modes, isolation masses are attached to all blades except for one blade in order to isolate that one blade from the rest of the structure. Ideally, the modes of the blisk with masses added (on all blades, except one) should all be pure cantilever blade like modes of the isolated blade without any contribution from the ones with masses added. In practice, there is still coupling between the isolated blade and the other blades. Thus, the method in [2] proposes a technique through which the contribution of the blades with masses added is quantified and included in the mistuning calculations. However, the identified mistuning obtained has a cyclic modeling error embedded that is not trivial to be identified. Thus, this paper enhances the procedure and directly identifies the blisk mistuning without the need to solve for a cyclic modelling error. To do so, the updated method considers a Taylor approximation of the eigenvalue of the blisk with one isolated blade and expresses it as a function of the detuning mass and the blisk

mistuning. In the Taylor expansion, the equation is centered about the eigenvalue of a tuned blisk with isolation masses and includes only the linear terms in the calculation. The coefficients of these linear terms are the so-called influence coefficients that are used through the identification process. In the current study, two blisks were considered: the UofM blisk with 24 blades and the OSU blisk having 22 blades. Mistuning identification was performed on both the computational models of the two blisks using mistuning values known a priori to be identified. The identification was successful with acceptable errors in the mistuning values at each blade. In addition, a mistuning identification was performed for the OSU as manufactured blisk. The method was capable of almost perfectly identifying one of two responding cantilever blade-like modes of the blisk blades with isolation masses added (on all blades, except one). However, the first responding cantilever beam like mode was not captured properly due to geometric differences between the computational and the as manufactured models of the OSU blisk. Future work involves analyzing the effect of adding second order terms to the Taylor expansion used in the identification procedure and to modify the OSU model to better match physical blisk.

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